

Evaluating knowledge and skills in Transfusion medicine among faculty of medicine university of Khartoum graduates

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Abstract

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BACKGROUND: The educational exposure to transfusion medicine within medical schools in Sudan is insufficient and lacks a standardized national curriculum. This deficiency has led to increase, often unnecessary, clinical use of blood transfusions and associated complications, underscoring the need for a comprehensive reform in medical training programs. The aim of this study is to assess the knowledge and skills of graduates from the Faculty of Medicine at the University of Khartoum regarding transfusion medicine.

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Methods:

This cross-sectional analytical study was carried out at the Faculty of Medicine, University of Khartoum, between September and November 2022. A total of 108 graduates participated, and data were obtained through a pre-coded structured questionnaire. Quantitative analysis was performed using SPSS, applying descriptive statistics and chi-square tests, while qualitative responses were examined using thematic analysis.

Results:

The findings demonstrated variable levels of knowledge and skills among graduates, with notable deficiencies in emergency transfusion protocols and blood storage practices. Many participants emphasized the need for additional time dedicated to transfusion medicine training, particularly in the form of field-based exposure and hands-on practical sessions.

Conclusions:

The study identified critical gaps in knowledge of emergency transfusion protocols and blood storage, underscoring the urgent need for curriculum reform in transfusion medicine education. It recommends strengthening practical training, extending course coverage, and adopting more effective teaching strategies to ensure better preparedness of future healthcare providers.

Keywords: Transfusion medicine; medical education; knowledge and skills; curriculum reform; University of Khartoum; Sudan

Introduction

The current curricula in medical schools lack exposure to transfusion medicine, and require reformulation of academic programs. In many medical schools training in blood transfusion is not currently offered. Clinical evidence indicates that blood transfusions occur more frequently than recommended and so do the complications related to this procedure. The rational use of blood requires improvement of both knowledge and skills in transfusion medicine. (1)

Multiple studies have recognized the gap between evidence-based and clinical practice they demonstrated limited transfusion knowledge and practice among medical school students, residents, fellows and faculty across specialties and concluded that there is a need for improvement. (2)

In Africa, the demand for effective transfusion services is accentuated by high incidences of maternal mortality, infectious diseases, and trauma injuries. However, the variability in educational standards, coupled with resource constraints, pose unique challenges to implementing effective transfusion medicine curricula. This disparity is more pronounced in regions with limited access to educational resources and expertise, making the need for curriculum evaluation and reform imperative. (3)

In Sudan ; The University of Khartoum, being a premier institution, has a pivotal role in shaping the future of healthcare professionals. However, there is a gap between the theoretical knowledge imparted by its transfusion medicine module and the practical skills required in clinical settings. This gap highlights a crucial area of concern in the education of medical students, potentially affecting the quality of care provided in Sudanese hospitals and clinics. (4)

Transfusion Medicine Academic Awards (TMAA) Program Sponsored by the National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute provided grants to medical schools to develop comprehensive curricula in transfusion medicine. This initiative aimed to standardize transfusion medicine education and ensure that medical students acquire the necessary knowledge and skills (5)

The TMAA program established a set of curricular goals and objectives for teaching transfusion medicine, designed to be integrated into the broader medical school curriculum. These goals covered a wide range of topics, from the basics of blood transfusion to advanced clinical applications (6)

In response to new developments in transfusion medicine and trends in medical education, the original TMAA curriculum was revised to reflect current practices and knowledge. The revised curriculum was designed to be more comprehensive and applicable to modern medical education settings (5)

The European and Mediterranean Initiative in Transfusion Medicine have advocated for standardized education in transfusion medicine across medical schools. These efforts aim to ensure that all medical graduates, regardless of their location, possess a basic understanding of transfusion practices and the ability to apply this knowledge in clinical settings (7)

Studies have been conducted to assess the current state of transfusion medicine education in medical schools. For instance, an analysis of medical curricula in Brazil revealed significant deficiencies in the teaching of transfusion medicine, highlighting the need for curriculum reform and the inclusion of dedicated transfusion medicine courses (8)

Despite efforts to improve transfusion medicine education, significant knowledge gaps remain among medical students and

residents. Continuous assessment and improvement of educational programs are necessary to ensure that future physicians are well-prepared to manage blood transfusions safely and effectively (9)

Integrating evidence-based transfusion medicine curricula into medical education can enhance the understanding and application of best practices in clinical settings. Educational programs should focus on the critical appraisal of transfusion literature and biostatistics to equip students with the skills needed for evidence-based practice (10)

A survey by Kupesiz et al. (2020) evaluated the self-perceived competency of final-year medical students in Turkey. The study revealed that a significant proportion of students felt unprepared to manage transfusion-related tasks, indicating a need for enhanced educational strategies and more practical training opportunities. (11)

A comprehensive understanding of emergency transfusion protocols and proper blood storage practices is essential for healthcare providers to ensure patient safety and optimize transfusion practices. This study aims to assess the knowledge and skills of graduates from the Faculty of Medicine, University of Khartoum, specifically focusing on their preparedness to handle transfusion-related situations effectively

Methods

Study Design This study utilized an analytic cross-sectional design.

Study Area: The research was conducted at the Faculty of Medicine, University of Khartoum, the oldest medical school in Sudan, established in 1924. It plays a crucial role in medical education, with both undergraduate and postgraduate programs. The undergraduate programs are six academic years after which the graduates awarded the MBBS degree, whereas the post graduate degrees are diplomas, Masters and Medical Doctoring degrees. In Khartoum university faculty of medicine serial changes happened to the undergraduates curriculum in the last decades and moving to outcome based & hybrid semester system was adopted since 2008

Study Population The study population graduates from the Faculty of Medicine during the period 2015 – 2018 who completed their education under the newly adopted semester system since 2009 and who had started their clinical practice. Those who had not yet begun clinical practice and those who were hematology registrars or specialists.

Sample Size The sample size for the graduate students was calculated using the formula: $n = N / (1 + N(e)^2)$. This calculation determined a sample size of 172 graduates, with feedback received from 108 graduates, resulting in a response rate of 62%.

Sampling Technique A simple random sampling technique was employed to select medical graduates from a list, ensuring each individual had an equal chance of selection.

Data Collection Methods Data were collected using the following tools:

Questionnaires: An online questionnaire was distributed to the study group.

It included personal data, clinical expertise details, knowledge and practice questions and graduates' opinion and suggestion for improvements in transfusion medicine. The questionnaire was pretested; and the content validity was determined by medical education experts. Reliability was determined after a pilot study.

Data Analysis: Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS software, version 25, employing descriptive statistics and the Chi-Square Test for significance, while Qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis, coding responses and interpreting themes to gain deeper insights.

Ethical Considerations: *Ethical approval was obtained from the Educational Development Center/Sudan Medical Specialization Board (EDC/SMSB). Written informed consent was provided to participants, ensuring confidentiality and anonymity throughout the study*

Results

Participant Demographics

The mean (\pm SD) age of participants was 29.49 (\pm 5.88) years, with a higher frequency of females (70, 64.8%) compared to males (38, 35.2%).

Clinical Experience of Graduates

Among the graduates, the most common current job was medical officer (51, 47.2%), followed by house officer (21, 19.4%), resident (18, 16.7%), and specialist (15, 13.9%). The majority of participants had one year of clinical experience (51, 47.2%), with others reporting four years (24, 22.2%), two years (23, 21.3%), and three years (10, 9.3%).

Knowledge of Transfusion Medicine

The assessment of graduates' knowledge revealed several critical findings: In cases of massive blood loss, 66.7% of graduates correctly identified packed red blood cells (PRBCs) and fresh frozen plasma as the

first two urgent components needed. For an alternative blood group to O-negative PRBCs in emergencies, 53% chose the correct answer, O-positive, while 35% did not know. Regarding the optimum storage conditions for platelet concentrates, only 37% selected the correct option of room temperature. The correct duration for completing PRBC transfusions (four hours) was identified by 27.8%, while a significant portion (28.7%) did not know the answer. When asked if their undergraduate education helped them in clinical practice, 45.5% responded positively, while 93.5% expressed the need for additional courses in clinical transfusion medicine before entering practice.

Practice of Transfusion Medicine

Participants demonstrated varied responses regarding practical aspects of transfusion medicine: When facing an immediate transfusion reaction, 91.7% correctly indicated that they would stop the blood transfusion. Writing details of transfusion reactions in patient records was practiced by 59%, while 29% admitted they did not document these details. Returning unused blood bags to blood banks was done by 59.3% of participants, indicating a gap in practice adherence. Overall Knowledge and Practice Assessment. Analysis of overall knowledge showed that 9.3% of participants had very weak knowledge, while 32.4% demonstrated strong knowledge. The mean knowledge score was 58.3 (SD 22.6), with a median of 66.6. Regarding practical skills, 50% of the graduates exhibited strong practice, with a mean practice score of 66.5 (SD 23.6) and a median of 66.67.

There was a significant relationship between knowledge and years of clinical

experience ($p = 0.032$), indicating that knowledge increased with greater clinical experience. Additionally, a significant relationship was observed between practice and clinical specialty ($p = 0.039$), particularly with obstetrics and gynecology showing strong practice levels.

Suggestions for Improvement

Graduates suggested several improvements for transfusion medicine education, with 77% advocating for more practical training and field experience, and 21% requesting additional time allocated to the module.

These results highlight critical gaps in knowledge and practice among graduates, emphasizing the need for substantial improvements in transfusion medicine education to better prepare future healthcare professionals.

Figure (3.2) Frequency distribution of overall Transfusion Medicine Knowledge among FMUK graduates,2021(n=108)

Figure (3.3) Frequency distribution of overall Transfusion Medicine Practice among FMUK graduates,2021(n=108)

Table (3.5) Cross table of the relationship between participants clinical data and Knowledge among FMUK graduates,2021(n=108)

Variable		Inadequate knowledge%	Adequate knowledge%	P-value
2. Gender	Female	30%	35%	0.078
	Male	15%	20%	
3.Current Job title:	House officer	14%	6%	0.110
	Medical officer	22%	28%	
	Resident	5%	12%	
	Specialist	4%	10%	
4.Clinical Specialty	Medicine	20%	27%	0.795
	Obse	5%	4%	
	Pediatrics	10%	14%	
	Surgery	9%	11%	
5. Years of clinical experience	One year	29%	18%	0.032
	Two year	5%	16%	
	Three years	5%	5%	
	Four years	6%	16%	
6. Do you have transfusion committee in your hospital?	I don't know	20%	17%	0.143
	No	16%	20%	
	Yes	8%	19%	

There is a significant relationship between knowledge and years of clinical experience (knowledge increase with increasing of years of experience p value less than 0.05)

Table(3.6) Cross table of the relationship between FMUK and Practice,2021(n=108)

Clinical data		Inadequate practice	Adequate practice	P-value
Gender	Female	17	53	0.721
	Male	11	27	
Current Job title:	House officer	6	15	0.142
	Medical officer	13	41	
	Resident	6	12	
	Specialist	3	12	
Clinical Specialty	Medicine	13	38	0.039
	Obse	1	8	
	Pediatrics	8	18	
	Surgery	6	17	
Years of clinical experience	One year	13	38	0.764
	Two year	6	17	
	Three years	3	7	
	Four years	6	18	
transfusion committee	I don't know	15	25	0.073
	No	10	29	
	Yes	3	26	

There is significant relationship between adequate practice and Obstetrics Clinical Specialty with P-value of 0.03

Discussion

Assessment of Graduate Knowledge and Practical Skills

The assessment of graduate knowledge and practical skills revealed varying levels of competency. While some graduates demonstrated strong theoretical knowledge, significant gaps were identified in areas such as emergency transfusion protocols and optimal storage conditions for blood products. This variability agrees with findings by Goel and Josephson, who noted that advances in transfusion practices, particularly for neonates and infants, require a comprehensive understanding that includes practical application (12) The identified knowledge gaps among graduates underscore the need for targeted educational interventions to enhance both theoretical understanding and practical skills.

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The statistical analysis revealed a moderate mean knowledge score with significant variability among graduates, indicating a need for more targeted educational interventions. The mean knowledge score of 58.33 and a practice score of 66.05 suggest that while some graduates have achieved a reasonable level of competence, others require additional support. This variability aligns with the findings of Dorée et al., who conducted a systematic review highlighting the inconsistencies in transfusion medicine education across different institutions and the need for standardized curricula to ensure uniformity in education and practice (13).

The analysis of graduate knowledge and skills in transfusion medicine indicates a clear trend: knowledge tends to increase with clinical experience. Graduates with more years of clinical experience consistently demonstrate higher levels of knowledge and competence in transfusion medicine practices. This trend underscores the importance of practical exposure and continuous learning in the medical field. This finding aligns with the general consensus in the literature that hands-on practice and real-world application are crucial for retaining and deepening medical knowledge; According to Goel and Josephson, ongoing clinical experience significantly enhances understanding and application of complex transfusion protocols, leading to better patient outcomes(12).

This aligns with the findings of Dorée et al., who emphasized that practical competence in transfusion medicine improves with consistent clinical practice and hands-on experience.

The data indicate that graduates with one to two years of experience are less confident and competent compared to those with three to four years of experience, highlighting the critical role of continuous clinical exposure in achieving and maintaining high levels of practical competence. (14)

Suggestions for Improvement Based on Graduate Feedback

The Faculty of medicine university of Khartoum graduates' emphasized the need for more practical sessions and extended course duration. There was also a suggestion to increase the load in exams to better assess students' understanding.

These recommendations are supported by literature indicating that practical training and comprehensive assessment methods are essential for effective learning and retention (15).

Implementing these suggestions could significantly enhance the transfusion medicine course, providing students with the necessary skills and knowledge to excel in their clinical practice.

By synthesizing these key findings with existing literature, critical areas for course improvement can be identified, and evidence-based recommendations can be provided to enhance transfusion medicine education at the University of Khartoum. Furthermore, graduates feedback highlighted the critical need for practical sessions and extended course duration to enhance learning outcomes. This aligns with Stout et al., who emphasized that incorporating more hands-on training and clinical exposure would bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, ultimately leading to better-prepared graduates. (16)

Integrating best practices such as simulation-based learning, hands-on practice, and e-learning platforms into the transfusion medicine course at the University of Khartoum can significantly enhance the effectiveness of the program. These methods provide a comprehensive educational experience that combines theoretical knowledge with practical skills, ensuring that graduates are well-prepared for clinical practice. By adopting these recommendations, the course can be improved to meet the highest standards of medical education, ultimately leading to better patient outcomes and a more competent healthcare workforce

Conclusions and Recommendations

Graduates displayed varying levels of knowledge and practical skills in transfusion medicine. While some graduates demonstrated strong knowledge, others had significant gaps, particularly in areas such as emergency transfusion protocols and optimal storage conditions for blood products.

- Graduates emphasized the need for more practical sessions and extended course duration. There was also a suggestion to increase the exam load to better assess students' understanding.

Limitations

- The limitations of the study are recall bias of the graduates ,the limited sample size and response rate also exclusion of other Stakeholders; as hospital administrators,health ministry officials and blood bank staff.

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This questioner is aiming to collect data about transfusion medicine education you have in semester six at undergraduate level and studying its impact on your clinical practice.

Your responses will help us so much to improve this course

If you agree to participate in this research please tick on I agree, you are free to apologize from participating and tick on disagree

I agree I disagree

Personal data:

1. Age

2. Gender a. Male b. Female

3. Current Job title: a. House officer b. Medical officer c. Resident
d. Specialist

4. Your hospital name

5. Which Clinical Specialty you work with now?

a. Medicine b. Surgery c. Obse d. Pediatrics

6. Years of clinical experience

a. One b. Two c. Three d. four

7. Do you have transfusion committee in your hospital?

a. Yes b. No c. I donot know

Regarding your clinical transfusion practice:

8. In cases of massive blood loss the best two ergent components you request are:

- a. Packed cells and platelets concentrate
- b. Fresh Frozen Plasma and Platelets concentrate
- c. Packed cells and Fresh Frozen Plasma
- d. I donot know

9. A- 60- years old male needed O -ve packed cells urgently, this blood group is not available at the blood bank, your option is to transfuse him with:

- a. B-ve
- b. A -ve
- c. O + ve
- d. I donot know

10. The storage of platelets concentrate is at:

- a. Refrigerator

b. Room temperature

c. Freezer

d. I donot know

11. After removal from refrigerator, The packed cells should be transfused within :

a. 30 min

b. One hour

c. Four hours

d. I donot know

12. When you face immediate transfusion reaction your first reaction is to:

a. Call for help

b. Stop blood transfusion

c. Ask for direct coombs test

d. I donot know

13. Do you practice writing the detail of transfusion reaction in patient card:

a. Yes b. No c. Some times

14. Do you return the unused blood bags to blood bank:

a. Yes b. No c. Some times

15. Do you think the course of transfusion medicine you have in your undergraduate study help you in your clinical practice

a. Yes b. No c. Some how

16 . Do you think more courses on clinical transfusion medicine are needed before practicing it:

a. Yes b. No c. I donot know

17. What is your suggestion for improvement of the undergraduate transfusion medicine course

1.....

2.....

3.....

Author Contributions

- Dr. Rihab Abdelhafiz Hassan Khattab: Conceived and designed the study, coordinated data collection, and contributed to drafting the manuscript.
- Dr. Alfatih Mohamed Malik: Supervised the methodology, performed data analysis and interpretation, and critically revised the manuscript for important intellectual content.
- Dr. Mohamed Elfatih Mustafa Khalil: Provided clinical expertise in orthopedics and trauma, supported literature review, and contributed to manuscript writing and final approval.

Declaration of Interests

- The authors declare no competing interests.

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